

in the eastern Mediterranean Sea (in particular, the Ionian Sea); it is an oligotrophic region which has become even more so since 1998. Coincidentally or not, this overlaps with one of the few parts of the basin in which MHW frequency has not significantly increased (Figure 2.7.2). Likewise, duration and intensity have also experienced little to no increase in this area. It is not known yet if there is a link between changes in extreme warming and biological productivity, yet our results provide motivation to explore this.

This study also acts as an inter-comparison of two reanalysis products against the long-term satellite-derived climate data record. GREP (product 2.7.2) is an ensemble of $\frac{1}{4}^\circ$ reanalyses and acts here as a representative of eddy-permitting resolution, while the high-res regional reanalysis captures finer scale dynamics. The three datasets largely agree on the relative trends between regions (e.g. all datasets suggest the western Mediterranean Sea have the largest maximum intensity trends compared to the other regions), yet the magnitude of these changes varies between the datasets, in particular for GREP. GREP has a tendency to overestimate intensity and duration, as well as the occurrence of higher-category events (though not always outside the confidence intervals of other products). The regional high-resolution reanalysis, meanwhile, typically has MHW statistic values closer to the satellite-derived product. The agreement of the high-res reanalysis and the satellite-derived product implies higher resolution makes an important difference in studying MHWs.

While the datasets agree on the evolution of the duration of moderate and strong events (Figure 2.7.4), there is greater disagreement on the severe and extreme MHWs. For example, the global reanalysis (product ref. 2.7.2) records longer severe events between 2007 and 2019, but none in the early 90s and 2000s. On the other hand the other datasets record severe and extreme events throughout the entire period (1993–2019). While the other datasets record severe and extreme events throughout the record. We note that the datasets have very different resolutions, and therefore different capabilities of incorporating mesoscale and sub-mesoscale drivers of MHWs. The level of agreement found here is nonetheless promising and will allow for further use of reanalyses, which will be necessary for study of the subsurface extent of MHWs and their role in mortality events (Garrabou et al. 2019).

The large confidence intervals in the trend calculations (purple ‘error bars’ in Figures 2.7.3 and 2.7.4) are a result of the high variability in MHW

characteristics over the past decades. For example, for the maximum intensity in the Adriatic Sea, the trend confidence interval is much larger than in the eastern Mediterranean Sea. Over the period studied, maximum intensity of MHWs is much more variable in the Adriatic Sea and is larger than in the eastern Mediterranean Sea (not shown); this is somewhat expected given the Adriatic Sea’s greater sensitivity to short-term atmospheric variability (Skirris et al. 2012; Zveryaev 2015).

Each MHW variable helps define potential ecological impacts, but their combined effect is key to a full understanding (Frölicher and Laufkötter 2018). For example, it is not known, and may depend on specific species, whether more frequent moderate events are more damaging than rare severe-extreme events. Ideally, datasets would agree on all MHW characteristic trends. However, to comment about the impacts on specific species would require the use of an absolute temperature threshold relevant to that species (e.g. Galli et al. 2017). Different species also have complex responses to extreme events, including the ability to recover from brief thermal stress (Hageunauer et al. 2013; Thompson et al. 2013). A constant barrage of weak events may be more hazardous than a single extreme event (e.g. Pitacco et al. 2018), and vice versa. The three datasets used here agree well on the increase in moderate and strong events, yet disagree on the occurrence of severe and extreme events (Figure 2.7.4). The disagreement between datasets on severe MHWs would hinder any analysis on species more susceptible to extraordinary, singular events. This further highlights the need, in future ecological hazard studies, to use more than one product. In the face of climate change and its economic and biological impacts through a substantial increase in a diversity of MHWs, this study can contribute to push towards more research in these areas. In particular, it can support further specific studies to help local policy makers and stakeholders (e.g. aquaculture, fisheries) better identify the regions of the Mediterranean Sea that are strategic for the early implementation of relevant adaptation pathways.

Section 2.8. Long-term interannual changes in extreme winds and waves in the Black Sea

Authors: Joanna Staneva, Marcel Ricker, Adem Akpinar, Arno Behrens, Rianne Giesen, Karina von Schuckmann

Statement of main outcome: This study aims to analyse long-term interannual changes in extreme winds and waves in the Black Sea. Severe wave conditions from 1979 to 2020 are detected using the 99th percentile of the significant wave height (SWH). Long-term

spatial wave statistics of the Black Sea are then obtained based on the annual trend of 99th percentile SWH and the number, lifetime, and intensity of extreme events occurring between 1979 and 2020. In addition, the variability of these extreme event characteristics is revealed. Wave reanalysis of the Black Sea is used to investigate intra-annual variation and long-term wave energy potential change. Wave power and wind statistics are shown for the Black Sea CMEMS multiyear products to identify the most suitable areas for wave energy exploitation and offshore wind power potential and to guide the safe and efficient design, installation and operation of marine energy sector assets. The results reveal that the average number of storm events is highest in the eastern basin. In contrast, the average lifetime reaches a maximum on the southwestern coast. Intensity peaks in the same region as the lifetime but is also high in the basin interior. Spatial mean extreme event analyses show a slight increase in event numbers and intensity but decreasing trends for the event lifetime and maximum area of storm events. In regions where wave conditions are strong, there have been increases in extremes relative to normal conditions in recent years. This can significantly affect designs. In terms of wave energy, mean wave power peaks in the southwestern area of the Black Sea. The wave power trend follows a pattern similar to that of the SWH with a pronounced east–west difference; its variation is higher, resulting in a coefficient of variation of ~ 2.5 .

Products used:

Ref. No.	Product name and type	Documentation
2.8.1	BLKSEA_MULTIYEAR_WAV_007_006, Model reanalysis	PUM: https://catalogue.marine.copernicus.eu/documents/PUM/CMEMS-BS-PUM-007-006.pdf QUID: https://catalogue.marine.copernicus.eu/documents/QUID/CMEMS-BS-QUID-007-006.pdf
2.8.2	ERA5 10 m (u, v) wind components. Years 1979–2020. Model reanalysis	https://www.ecmwf.int/en/forecasts/datasets/reanalysis-datasets/era5
2.8.3	WIND_GLO_WIND_L3_REP_OBSERVATIONS_012_005 Satellite wind data	PUM: https://catalogue.marine.copernicus.eu/documents/PUM/CMEMS-WIND-PUM-012-002-005.pdf

(Continued)

Continued.

Ref. No.	Product name and type	Documentation
2.8.4	AVISO wind and significant wave height	QUID: https://catalogue.marine.copernicus.eu/documents/QUID/CMEMS-WIND-QUID-012-002-003-005.pdf ftp-access.aviso.altimetry.fr

2.8.1. Introduction

In the last decade, the European seas have been hit by severe storms, causing serious damage to offshore infrastructure and coastal zones and drawing public attention to the importance of having reliable and comprehensive wave forecasts/hindcasts, especially during extreme events. In addition, human activities such as the offshore wind power industry, the oil industry, and coastal recreation regularly require climate and operational information on maximum wave height at a high resolution in space and time (Benetazzo et al. 2021). Thus, there is a broad consensus that a high-quality wave climatology and predictions and a deep understanding of extreme waves caused by storms could substantially contribute to coastal risk management and protection measures, thereby preventing or minimising human and material damage and losses.

In addition, extreme waves can have serious impacts on the coastal environment and infrastructures (Benetazzo et al. 2021). Amarouche et al. (2020) assessed storm events and their potential impacts on the West Mediterranean Sea coasts. The authors found a progressive increase in the number of storm events and their intensity over the last decade and noted the increased damage recently recorded on the Algiers coastlines and the nature of coastal storm damages at the local scale depend on several factors, mainly the power of these storms and their direction given the complex morphology of the Algiers coastlines. Sea state information impacts are directed towards the improvement of the definition of environmental loads over the lifetime of a ship or structure (e.g. wind energy turbines or oil and gas platforms). For example, long-term statistics and high-resolution predictions of SWH are necessary for planning the maintenance operations of offshore wind farms. Subject to wave forecasts, ‘go/no go’ decisions are made on all operations and maintenance activities in offshore wind farms in the days and hours preceding a mission. Indeed, a reduction in the uncertainties of metocean conditions will have a direct impact on structure and mooring loads (both

for the ultimate limit state and fatigue design) and on warning criteria for ships. In addition, the design of coastal and offshore structures requires a reliable estimation of extreme wave parameters (Benetazzo et al. 2021; Le Traon et al. 2021). This information can be obtained through hindcast and forecast studies that apply extreme wave parameters, which are also aimed at expanding the wave CMEMS product catalogue by providing novel wave diagnostics.

Long-term wave statistics for the Black Sea are critical to the safe and efficient design, installation and operation of marine energy sector assets (Akpınar et al. 2016). High-resolution regional and coastal wave models can help improve the downscaling of general sea state forecasts, locate hotspots of different wave height properties and correctly prioritise maintenance jobs for offshore wind turbines, reducing their maintenance costs. Applications can further include initial resource assessment (wave power), environmental assessment, and planning (e.g. for installation and execution, operation and maintenance).

Spectral models have made significant improvements over the last decades in predicting bulk wave parameters, such as the SWH, wave periods and directions, and they continue to constitute an essential part of marine weather analysis (Álvarez Fanjul et al. 2019; Bingölbali et al. 2020; Cavaleri et al. 2020). As a result, SWH in the global seas (ECMWF 2019) and in the Mediterranean and Black Seas (see, e.g. Arkhipkin et al. 2014; Akpınar et al. 2016; Sartini et al. 2017) has been thoroughly assessed. Studies assessing wave energy potential in the Black Sea have been performed by Rusu (2009), Akpınar and Kömürcü (2012, 2013), Rusu (2019), Akpınar et al. (2017, 2019), Von Schuckmann et al. (2020), Staneva et al. (2020a), Le Traon et al. (2021), and Bingölbali et al. (2020, 2021). Previous studies of the Black Sea mostly focus on mean conditions or individual storms, whereas here, we analyse extreme conditions. Description and statistics of maximum wave parameters (maximum wave height H_m and crest height) of the 1993–2018 climatology of the Black Sea and the Mediterranean Sea in wave models WAM and WAVEWATCH III are shown in Benetazzo et al. (2021) and Le Traon et al. (2021). Here, analyses of extreme wind and wave conditions and wave power statistics are obtained from the recent CMEMS Black Sea long-term wave reanalysis (product ref 2.8.1; Staneva et al. 2020b).

2.8.2. Methodology

2.8.2.1. WAM model description

The Black Sea Wave Analysis and Forecasting System is based on the WAM Cycle 6 Black Sea model (spatial

resolution of approximately 3 km), which replaced Cycle 4.6.2 (operational since April 2017) within the CMEMS in December 2020 (product ref. 2.8.1; Staneva et al. 2020b). The regional wave model for the semi-enclosed Black Sea runs in a shallow water mode with a spatial resolution of approximately 3 km. WAM calculates the two-dimensional energy density spectrum at each of the 44,699 active model grid points in frequency and directional space. The solution of the energy balance equation is provided for 24 directional bands at 15° each, starting at 7.5° and measured clockwise with respect to true north and with 30 frequencies logarithmically spaced from 0.042 to 0.66 Hz at intervals of $\Delta f/f = 0.1$. To include the important contribution of higher frequency waves to wave growth/dissipation processes and the output wave characteristics, a parametric tail is fitted for frequencies exceeding the spectral maximum (e.g. WAMDI 1988). Detailed descriptions are given by Komen et al. (1994), Janssen and Bidlot (2018), and Staneva et al. (2019). The basic physics and numeric are maintained in the new release. The source function integration scheme developed by Hersbach et al. (2000) and model updates by Bidlot et al. (2007) are incorporated. Wave model performance is discussed in Staneva et al. (2021). The parameterisation of the wave growth in the wind input source term has been adapted to the driving wind fields. The WAM model estimates sea state-dependent momentum and energy fluxes, and Stokes-Coriolis forcing diagnostics are needed to couple to ocean models (Staneva et al. 2017). Wave-induced processes have been shown to have a significant impact on drift estimations, e.g. Staneva et al. (2021). WAM cycle 6.0 included the new extreme wave diagnostics (maximal wave height and wave crest, Benetazzo et al. 2021) in the new datasets. Wave breaking parameterisation is taken into account, but the time-dependent depth and current fields are not included in Black Sea wave reanalyses (product ref 2.8.1). A novel feature of the Black Sea reanalysis data is that radar altimeter data are assimilated. In addition to SWH, the assimilation includes wind speed data. The required radar altimeter data for this purpose are taken from AVISO (<ftp-access.avisio.altimetry.fr>; product ref. 2.8.4). The measurements are assimilated into the wave model using an optimal interpolation scheme. Due to a lack of available systematic in situ observations for the Black Sea, satellite data bring added value to wave simulations. The reanalysis simulation covers the period 1 January 1979 to 31 December 2020 (product ref. 2.8.1); that is, in total, trends for 42 years have been simulated with an hourly output time step. Reference Jason-1 data are available for the first period of 15/01/2002 to 21/06/2013, Jason-2 data are available for

22/06/2013 to 30/06/2019 and Jason-3 data are available for 01/07/2019 to 31/12/2019 (product ref. 2.8.4). Making use of the annual time scale provides enough samples to examine quantiles of even higher than the 99th percentile, supporting understanding of peak values in the western part of the Black Sea. A close match of the Black Sea CMEMS data to the satellite measurements for high waves is observed (Von Schuckmann et al. 2020).

2.8.2.2. Wind data

The driving forces for the wave model are the hourly ERA5 10-m wind reanalyses of ECMWF (Hersbach et al. 2020, product ref. 2.8.2). The quality of ERA5 data for the Black Sea was recently investigated in Çalışır et al. (2021) against altimeter and scatterometer satellite data. It has been shown that ERA5 and Climate Forecast System Reanalysis (CFSR) underestimate wind speeds; however, ERA5 winds have less bias and are more scattered than CFSR winds against the satellite data. Here, wind forcing analyses are performed against the L3 satellite wind observations of METOP-A ASCAT with a spatial resolution of 0.125° (Stoffelen et al. 2017; product ref. 2.8.3). The available period of the METOP-A ASCAT data covers 2007–2020 and combines the ascending and descending satellite tracks by using their mean at each time step. To infer statistical quantities, the satellite wind observations are processed as in the ERA5 reanalyses. Changes in extreme ASCAT wind speeds over the Global Ocean are analysed in Giesen and Stoffelen (this issue).

2.8.2.3. Analysis of the storm events

Extreme wave characteristics are studied by analysing single storm events and their long-term means and trends. These storm events were detected using the method proposed by Weisse and Günther (2007). The basis of the method is the definition of a severe event threshold (SET), which we define as the 99th percentile of the SWH (Figure 2.8.1(a)). Then, the exceedance and shortfall of the SWH at every grid point was determined and counted as a storm event (Figure 2.8.1(d)). The time period between each exceedance and shortfall of the SET is the lifetime of an event (Figure 2.8.1(g)). The difference in the maximum SWH of each event and the SET is defined as the event intensity (Figure 2.8.1(j)). The geographic area of storm events and exceedance of the SET are defined as the maximum event area. The number, lifetime, and intensity of events were averaged over the year. Finally, the yearly values were used to compute the long-term means presented in Figure 2.8.1 (left column). In addition, for these parameters, we estimated the anomaly of 2020 from the

long-term mean (middle column) and the linear trend (right column). To show multiyear variability (Figure 2.8.2), each event, fulfilling the above-described definition, is considered in the statistics. This was done independent of the events' locations within the domain. To obtain long-term trends, a linear regression was applied to the yearly time series. Trends are computed using the nonparametric Sen's slope estimator for robust linear regression.

2.8.2.4. Wave power characterisation

The wave power was obtained as a prognostic model output using the following formula:

$$P = \frac{\rho g^2}{64\pi} H_s^2 T_e \approx 0.48 H_s^2 T_e,$$

where ρ is water density, g is acceleration due to gravity, H_s is the significant wave height, and T_e is the wave energy period. A variety of standard statistics, such as the standard deviation, specific percentiles, and the maximum were determined as yearly averages. In addition, the Coefficient of Variation (CoV) was computed and is defined as the standard deviation divided by the long-term mean.

2.8.3. Results

Long-term wave statistics of the Black Sea were derived by considering three important features (the mean, the 2020 anomaly, and the linear trend) of four characteristics described in the previous section (the 99th percentile SWH, yearly average number, lifetime, and intensity of storm events), and the results are presented in Figure 2.8.1. The 99th SWH mean percentile for 1979–2019 (Figure 2.8.1(a)) shows a similar pattern to that of previous analyses using the CMEMS wave products (Álvarez Fanjul et al. 2019; Staneva et al. 2020a), demonstrating that the highest values of the mean annual 99th percentile, above 3.5 m, occur in the western Black Sea, while the 99th percentile values of the eastern part of the basin are approximately 2.5 m. This pattern is also consistent with previous studies (Akpınar et al. 2016 and Van Vledder and Akpınar 2016). The anomaly of the 99th percentile for 2020 is mostly negative (Figure 2.8.1(b)); the highest positive anomalies of the 99th percentile for 2020 (ca. 60 cm) are located in the southwestern section of the Black Sea. This result correlates well with the anomaly of the wind speed for 2020 (Figure 2.8.2). The yearly mean lifetime of storm events (Figure 2.8.1(g)) reached maximum values (approximately 20 h) in and around Burgas Bay and reached values of over 15 h in the coastal part of the southwestern Black Sea from the Gulf of Kavarna to Bosphorus. In the

Figure 2.8.1. Long-term wave statistics of the Black Sea. Significant wave height (a) 1979–2019 99th percentile, (b) 2020 99th percentile anomaly, and (c) 1979–2020 linear trend of 99th percentile. (d), (g), and (j) yearly average number of storm events, (e), (h), and (k) lifetime of storm events, and (f), (i), and (l) intensity of storm events for the same periods as in (a)–(c). The analyses are based on yearly averages obtained from product ref. 2.8.1.

remaining areas, the average annual lifetime of storm events exceeds 7.5 h. Figure 2.8.1(d) also shows that the yearly mean number of storm events is low in regions where the average annual lifetime and intensity of storms are high. In contrast, the number of events is high where their lifetime and intensity are low. The mean intensity of the events (Figure 2.8.1(j)) reaches the highest values (approximately 1 m) in the Bosphorus and Sakarya canyons in the southwestern area of the Black Sea. While the southwest Black Sea is exposed to yearly mean storm event numbers of below the long-term averages (Figure 2.8.1(d)), it is observed that the yearly mean lifetime of the events in the same region is higher than the long-term averages (Figure 2.8.1(g)). As expected, the extreme wave statistics based on the 99th percentile threshold of the SWH are very similar to the wind sea wave parameter, and the swell contribution is much lower (not shown here). In terms of the mean intensity of events, in 2020, more severe waves occurred in the coastal region between Bosphorus and Burgas Bay and in the region narrowing

and extending from this region to the open waters, more than 1 m over the long-term average (Figure 2.8.1(k)). This in part explains the damage that has occurred in these regions in recent years.

To visualise the time behaviour of the wave extremes, we show spatially averaged 42-year time series of the number, lifetime, and intensity of extreme events (Figure 2.8.3). Extreme wave heights were validated against the observations given in Staneva et al. (2020a). Over the entire period, the number and intensity of events increased, while the lifetime and area of extreme events slightly decreased. This long-term development can be decomposed into a decrease in the frequency of severe wave events from 1979 until 1986, an increase between 2000–2005 and 2011–2016 and an attenuation in the intensity and duration of these events from approximately 2002–2010. This development is mainly due to the wind sea waves. In recent years, trends in the number of severe wave events closely correspond to the reported evolution of the annual 99th percentile of the SWH (Staneva et al. 2020a).

Figure 2.8.2. Long-term wind statistics of the Black Sea obtained from the METOP-A satellite (upper row; product ref. 2.8.3) as well as ERA5 (lower row; product ref. 2.8.2). The considered periods start in 2007 and 1979, respectively. (a) and (d) 99th percentile until 2019, (b) and (e) 2020 99th percentile anomaly, and (c) and (f) linear trend of 99th percentile until 2020. The analyses are based on yearly averages.

We also analyse the linear trends of 1979–2020 for different severe wave event characteristics. The SWH trend for 1979–2020 reveals an east–west difference with a dominant negative difference in the western region and a positive difference in the eastern region (not shown here). Along the western and southwestern coasts, the trend of the 99th percentile of the SWH is positive (Figure 2.8.1(c)). Notably, this is also the area where the mean lifetime of events reaches a maximum (Figure 2.8.1(h)). The yearly change in the frequency of events is positive overall except along the Crimean Peninsula and in the southern Black Sea (Figure 2.8.1(f)). In contrast, the lifetime trend (Figure 2.8.1(i)) is mostly negative (-10 min/year), and only in some areas along the northwestern and southern coasts and the eastern Black Sea is the lifetime of extreme events increasing. Along the southwestern Black Sea coast, the yearly mean lifetime and intensity of events reach their maxima, while the number of events is small relative to the rest of the basin. The analyses show that in the regions where wave conditions are strong, there have been increases in extremes relative to normal conditions in recent years. This can significantly affect designs for infrastructure.

It can be inferred that the increase in the 99th percentile SWH in the southeastern part of the model domain is mainly caused by an increase in the number of extreme events, whereas their duration shows no significant change. Along the southwestern coast, all extreme statistics show a positive trend. In contrast, in the central Black Sea, there were no significant changes in the number of severe events, whereas the average duration of extreme events exhibited a slightly negative trend of

up to 5 min/year, which was probably caused by wind changes. In summary, the analyses show that the average number of storm events is the highest in the eastern basin. In contrast, the average lifetime reaches its maximum on the southwestern coast. The intensity reaches its maximum in the same region as the lifetime but is also high in the basin interior. The different causes of the described changes in extreme wave climate may have implications for different applications. For example, coastal marine constructions (e.g. levees) are likely to be more sensitive to the duration than to the number of extreme wave events, whereas for navigation, the number of days with no or only restricted services due to heavy seas may be an issue.

The 99th percentiles of wave power mean patterns for 1979–2020 are overall consistent with the SWH (Figure 2.8.4(a), and Staneva et al. 2020a). The spatial pattern of mean annual wave power echoes the findings of Valchev et al. (2013), Rusu (2019), and Akpınar et al. (2017). The maximum 99th percentile of wave power is observed in the southwestern Black Sea. There are hardly any changes in wave power in the southeastern Black Sea (Figure 2.8.4(c)). The changes in wave power are positive in surrounding areas of the Danube Delta and along the western Black Sea coast. A slight and nonsignificant increasing trend is observed along the eastern Black Sea coastal areas. Offshore in the central Black Sea and west of the Crimean Peninsula, the 99th percentile of the wave power trend is decreasing. The pattern of the anomaly of the 99th percentile of wave power in 2020 (Figure 2.8.4(b)) correlates well with that of the wind speed anomaly in 2020 (Figure 2.8.2), revealing a positive wave-power anomaly in the

Figure 2.8.3. Yearly (a) number, (b) lifetime, (d) intensity, and (f) maximum event area. The dashed lines denote the linear regression (c), (e), and (g) are the respective histograms. The histograms have the following bin sizes: 5 h, 0.1 m, 0.05 km^2 , respectively. The analyses take into account the whole model domain and are based on product ref. 2.8.1. Long-term spatial mean storm analyses of the Black Sea based on 42-year CMEMS wave reanalyses show almost no trend in event numbers (0.029 ± 0.275 events/year), a slight increase of their intensity (0.774 ± 2.938 cm/year) but decreasing trends in the event lifetime (-0.021 ± 0.061 h/year) and event area of extremes (-5.903 ± 169.676 km^2 /year).

Figure 2.8.4. Long-term wave power statistics of the Black Sea. (a) 1979–2019 99th percentile, (b) 2020 99th percentile anomaly, and (c) 1979–2020 linear trend of 99th percentile. (d) Standard deviation, (e) maximum, and (f) coefficient of variation of the period 1979–2020. The analyses are based on yearly averages derived from product ref. 2.8.1.

southwestern Black Sea and a negative anomaly in the central basin.

The long-term variability of the mean wave energy potential is critical for the wave energy sector. The overall economic profitability of a given site can be evaluated in terms of average energy production taking into account its distribution over wave heights, periods and directions. A significant factor in this evaluation is inter-annual fluctuation, demonstrated here with the mean pattern of the coefficient of variation (Figure 2.8.4(f)). A lower variation coefficient, in combination with sufficiently high wave energy flux, can indicate that a specific area is promising for a stable wave energy production. The Crimean coast and the area along eastern coastline show to be the most pronounced inter-annual variability. It is important to notice here that in the regions with the highest average wave power, the inter-annual variability is relatively low. On the north-western shelf and along the southern coast the variability is very low.

2.8.4. Discussion and conclusions

Long-term changes in extreme wave conditions are difficult to detect and to analyse because of the rare occurrence of these events as well as their limited spatial and temporal extent. Analyses of long-term changes require long and homogeneous time series that cover the area of interest at high spatial and temporal detail, a requirement that is frequently not fulfilled by the available observational data. Wave reanalysis data produced by wave model simulations together with data assimilation have therefore become a common tool to complement existing observations and to analyse trends

and variability of severe wave events at different scales (e.g. ERA-5 wave analyses, CMEMS products). Here we used a recent CMEMS wave reanalysis (Staneva et al. 2020b) for the Black Sea covering the past 42 years (1979–2020). The reanalysis are produced using the: (1) WAM Cycle 6.0 state-of-the-art wave model that includes new dissipation term parameterisations introduced by Ardhuin et al. (2010) and ECMWF (2020), (2) switching to highfrequency atmospheric analyses data of ECMWF ERA-5 and data assimilation of along-track SWH observations, (3) using satellite observation data assimilation. The time evolution of the percentile-based storm indices closely follows that described for the 99th percentile of the significant wave height in the Black Sea area.

The major findings are as follows:

- The average number of storm events is the highest in the eastern basin. In contrast, the average life time has its maximum at the southwestern coast. The Intensity has its maximum in the same region as the life time but is also high in the basin interior.
- The different causes of the described changes in extreme wave climate may have different implications for different applications. For example, coastal marine constructions (e.g. levees) are likely to be more sensitive to the duration than to the number of extreme wave events, whereas for the navigations the number of days with no or only restricted services because of heavy seas may be an issue.
- The impact statistics for events show no significant trends on the Black Sea basin scales. Only the 99th percentile trend is slightly negative.

- The storm analyses show that the yearly average number of storm events is the highest in the eastern basin. In contrast, the average life time has its maximum at the southwestern coast. The intensity has its maximum in the same region as the life time but is also high in the basin interior.
- Long-term spatial mean storm analyses for the Black Sea show based on the 42-year CMEMS reanalyses show slight increase of event numbers and intensity, but decreasing trends for event life time and maximum area.
- The mean wave power has its maximum in the southwest of the Black Sea. Compared to the mean wave heights, its variation is much higher resulting in a CoV of ~2.5 (~0.75 for mean wave height). The wave power trend has a similar pattern compared to the one of the wave height with a pronounced east–west difference.

In the agreement signed between MOI and the ‘European Commission’ is stated that future Copernicus Marine Service will ‘aim to better support EU policies and directives, increase its user base beyond Europe and in emerging blue markets such as ocean energy, desalinisation or blue biotechnology and infrastructure (see the Blue Economy report 2021)’. The study here contributed to the ocean energy sector. We propose new OMIs that are the trend of the frequency and lifetime of the events and the CoV of wave power.

Funding

This research was funded by the Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service for the Black Sea Monitoring and Forecasting Center (Contract 21002L4-COP-MFC BS-5400) and the EU H2020 Project ‘Developing Optimal and Open Research Support for the Black Sea’ (DOORS), grand agreement: 101000518.

Section 2.9. The Black Sea overturning circulation and its indicator of change

Authors: Mehmet Ilicak, Salvatore Causio, Stefania Ciliberti, Giovanni Coppini, Leonardo Lima, Ali Aydogdu, Diana Azevedo, Rita Lecci, Derin U. Cetin, Simona Masina, Elisaveta Peneva, Murat Gunduz, Nadia Pinardi
Statement of the main outcome: The Black Sea (BS) is the largest deep estuarine basin in the world. Its meridional overturning circulation (BS-MOC) is here described for the first time: in particular, the BS-MOC interannual variability in both depth and density space has been computed using a state-of-the-art ocean

reanalysis provided in the framework of the Copernicus Marine Service for the Black Sea of 28 year-period (1993–2020) for the definition of a new climate index. The mean meridional streamfunction defined for the upper 150 m in the depth space reveals an anticlockwise cell in the southern part of the Black Sea coming from the injection of the Mediterranean waters through the Bosphorus Strait into the Black Sea and a clockwise cell in the northern part of the Black Sea as a manifestation of the Cold Intermediate Layer (CIL). The new index is then defined as maximum overturning circulation in density space between 22.45 and 23.85 kg m⁻³. For the overall period, the BS-MOC index weakened between 1993 and 2010 from 0.13 Sv down to 0.07 Sv, then it recovered and has equilibrated around 0.1 Sv. Additionally, it shows a very strong correlation with the CIL from observational data, supporting the concept of using such an indicator to understand and monitor the water mass formation in the Black Sea basin.

Product used:

Ref. No.	Product name & type	Documentation
2.9.1	BLKSEA_MULTIYEAR_PHY_007_004 Ocean reanalysis	PUM: https://resources.marine.copernicus.eu/documents/PUM/CMEMS-BS-PUM-007-004.pdf QUID: https://catalogue.marine.copernicus.eu/documents/QUID/CMEMS-BS-QUID-007-004.pdf
2.9.2	SDC_BLS_CLIM_TS_V2 SeaDataCloud Black Sea Temperature and Salinity Climatology V2: temperature and salinity climatology for the Black Sea combining data from (1) SeaDataNet infrastructure, (2) World Ocean Database, and (3) Coriolis Ocean Dataset for Reanalysis for the period 1955–2019	DOI: https://doi.org/10.12770/847f1627-f39f-40af-b3b0-a2f6d29ff4dc Reference: Volodymyr Myroshnychenko (2020). <i>SeaDataCloud Black Sea Temperature and Salinity Climatology V2</i> . https://doi.org/10.12770/847f1627-f39f-40af-b3b0-a2f6d29ff4dc
2.9.3	Black_Sea_CIL_Cold_Content_Annual.nc Spatial and annual averages of the Cold Intermediate Layer in the Black Sea derived	DOI: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3691960

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